

First-principles investigation of gas adsorption on bilayer transition metal dichalcogenides for sensing toxic gases

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ABSTRACT

Transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) have shown significant promise in gas sensing applications due to their high catalytic activity and unique electronic properties, which facilitate effective interactions with various gas molecules. This makes them ideal candidates for high-performance gas sensors. In this study, we investigated the sensing properties of nitrogen-containing gases (NCGs) on several heterostructures—namely, MoS₂/WTe₂, MoTe₂/WS₂, MoS₂/TiO₂ and MoS₂/IrO₂—using density functional theory calculations. The results indicate that NH₃ and NO_x exhibit weak electronic interactions with MoS₂/WTe₂ and MoTe₂/WS₂ heterostructures, while strong electronic interactions are observed with MoS₂/TiO₂ and MoS₂/IrO₂ heterostructures. Electron transport properties were further assessed using Non-Equilibrium Green's Function calculations, revealing promising gas sensing characteristics for NH₃ detection across all heterostructures and particularly effective NO_x detection with MoS₂/WTe₂ and MoTe₂/WS₂ heterostructures. These findings highlight the potential of MoS₂/WTe₂ and MoTe₂/WS₂ as sensitive and selective gas sensors for both NH₃ and NO_x, providing valuable insights for developing advanced gas-sensing technologies with diverse practical applications.

Introduction

Today, the world faces critical challenges from air pollution and the greenhouse effect, which lead to significant public health issues and environmental degradation [1–3]. According to the World Health Organization, millions of people die each year due to exposure to toxic gases in the air, which damages both the circulatory and respiratory systems [4–7]. Among the primary pollutants in the environment are nitrogen-containing gases, such as nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and ammonia (NH₃), which are primarily emitted by the petrochemical industry and vehicles. Nitrogen oxides, including nitric oxide and nitrogen dioxide (NO_x), are highly toxic and have severe impacts on human and animal metabolic processes. Even at low concentrations, NO_x can damage the human respiratory system, potentially leading to various diseases. Additionally, NH₃ reacts rapidly with other gases, posing further risks by irritating the respiratory system, depositing in the lungs, and, in extreme cases, leading to loss of life [8–13]. Given these dangers, detecting and capturing harmful gases is essential for safeguarding human health and the environment. This urgent need has driven our efforts to design new sensing materials capable of detecting toxic gases. Gas sensors, which are indispensable for monitoring hazardous air pollutants, have recently

gained attention for their applications in human health monitoring, environmental pollution assessment, military and public safety, wearable devices, and smart farming [14–19].

Developing high-performance gas sensors requires devices that maintain high stability, sensitivity, and selectivity. As a result, recent studies have focused on novel sensing materials, with metal oxide sensors receiving significant attention due to their low cost, small particle size, and ease of production. However, metal oxide sensors are limited by specific working conditions and stability, which restricts their sensitivity [20–26]. Consequently, it is essential to explore gas sensing materials that operate at room temperature, with high sensitivity, a large surface-to-volume ratio, and a strong binding force for gas adsorption. In this regard, two-dimensional materials have become an area of intense study, given their large surface-to-volume ratios, high mobility of surface charge carriers, and atomic-thin layered structures that make them ideal for high-performance sensors [21,27–29]. Among these materials, transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) offer excellent physical, chemical, and mechanical properties suitable for nano-electronic devices. Due to their tunable structures, numerous reactive sites, and high surface-to-volume ratios, TMDs are promising candidates for sensing devices [30–35].

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Both theoretical and experimental studies have demonstrated that TMDs are excellent sensors for toxic gases, [36–38]. The sensing mechanism of TMDs is based on charge transfer during gas adsorption. Recent research has focused on monolayer MoS₂-based sensors, which can detect NO₂ at sub-ppb levels (20 ppb) and NH₃ at 1 ppm [39–42]. Investigations by Babar et al. on monolayer and few-layer MoS₂ and WS₂ have revealed these materials' sensitivity and stability in detecting nitrogen-containing gases and carbon monoxide. Their studies show that MoS₂ and WS₂ bilayers and heterobilayers exhibit excellent gas-sensing performance [20,22]. In our previous studies, we investigated various heterostructures and developed a single device incorporating a triboelectric nanogenerator [43]. This nanogenerator not only enhanced power output but also provided a stable power source, which is valuable for sensor applications requiring consistent power. In this study, we used selected heterostructures from previous work to investigate their toxic gas sensing capabilities. We examined adsorption energies for all gases and electronic properties, including electron density differences, Bader charge analysis, and density of states. Additionally, we evaluated the sensitivity of the selected structures by analyzing their current–voltage characteristics before and after gas adsorption.

Computational details

In our study, we examined various heterostructures of MX₂ materials, where M represents elements such as Mo and W, and X includes S, Te, and O. Specifically, we investigated the heterostructures MoS₂/WTe₂, MoTe₂/WS₂, MoS₂/TiO₂ and MoS₂/IrO₂. All density functional theory calculations were performed using the SIESTA 4.1.5 package [44,45]. We utilized Troullier–Martins-type norm-conserving pseudopotentials in our calculations [46]. The core radii for each atom were used as specified in the pseudopotential parameters without modification. Ir (s-3.14, p-4.40, d-2.30, f-3.51 a₀), Mo (s-1.06, p-1.35, d-2.17, f-2.62 a₀), O (s-0.77, p-1.77 a₀), S (s-1.35, p-2.04 a₀), Ti (s-0.91, p-0.95, d-0.89, f-2.99 a₀), Te (s-2.96, p-2.75, d-3.66 a₀), W (s-3.39, p-2.64, d-2.58, f-2.49 a₀). Based on previous simulations of similar heterostructures [47,48], we selected the van der Waals energy functional parameterized by Lee et al. [49]. As 2D heterostructures are primarily held by dispersion forces, the van der Waals density functional(vdW-DF2) exchange functional has been considered into the calculations [50,51]. We employed a double-zeta basis set with polarization functions (DZP) for our calculations. Following benchmark calculations, the electronic properties and geometry optimizations were investigated using the Monkhorst–Pack grid method, with a k-point sampling of 11 x 11 x 1 and the kinetic energy cutoff was set to 700 eV to ensure computational accuracy and efficiency. A 3 × 3 supercell was used for adsorption calculations and atomic positions were relaxed using a conjugate gradient algorithm until force and energy tolerances were below 0.01 eV/Å and 1x10⁻⁵ eV, respectively. A vacuum-slab was utilized along the c-axis to prevent interactions among periodic images. The lattice mismatch between distinct TMD layers in the heterostructures is addressed by introducing a small amount of strain to align the lattice parameters of the layers. This approach ensures that the two layers match in periodicity, enabling the construction of a commensurate supercell suitable for computational simulations. The applied strain is carefully controlled to remain minimal, typically within a few percent, to prevent significant distortions or artifacts in the structural and electronic properties of the heterostructure. Structural relaxation is then performed to allow the system to adjust naturally and achieve a stable, low-energy configuration, ensuring the accuracy of subsequent calculations. The adsorption energy (E_{ads}) of gas molecules on TMD bilayers was calculated using the following formula:

$$E_{\text{ads}} = E_{\text{TMD/gas}} - E_{\text{TMD}} - E_{\text{gas}} \quad (1)$$

Here, $E_{\text{TMD/gas}}$ represents the total energy of the system with gas adsorption, E_{TMD} is the energy of TMD bilayers, and E_{gas} is the energy of

gas molecules.

For investigating the electronic transport properties of the sensing systems, we calculated the current–voltage (I-V) characteristics using the TranSIESTA code, which employs the Non-Equilibrium Green's Function approach [52,53]. Gold was used as the electrode material, with the scattering region and semi-infinite left and right electrodes forming part of the device. Both electrodes were connected to the scattering region. The transport electric current was calculated using the Landauer–Büttiker formula which is described as follows [54].

$$\frac{2e}{h} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} T(E, V_b) [f_L(E - \mu_L) - f_R(E - \mu_R)] dE = I(V_b) \quad (2)$$

Here, f_L and f_R represent the Fermi–Dirac distribution functions of the left and right electrodes, respectively; e is the electron charge; $I(V_b)$ denotes the electric current under the applied bias voltage V_b ; μ_L and μ_R are the chemical potentials of the left and right electrodes, respectively; and h is the reduced Planck's constant. The chemical potentials of the two electrodes shift up and down relative to the Fermi energy E_F due to the applied bias voltage.

$$\mu_{L(R)} = E_F \pm \frac{eV_b}{2} \quad (3)$$

$T(E, V_b)$ is the transmission coefficient, describing the probability of electron transport at a given energy E under the applied bias V_b .

$$T(E, V_b) = \text{Tr}[\Gamma_L(E, V_b)G(E, V_b)\Gamma_R(E, V_b)G^*(E, V_b)] \quad (4)$$

The retarded and advanced Green's functions are represented by $G(E, V_b)$ and $G^*(E, V_b)$, respectively. Γ_L and Γ_R denote the contact broadening functions associated with the left and right electrodes, respectively, describing the coupling between the transport region and the electrodes [55]. During the transport calculations, the k-point sampling was set to $13 \times 1 \times 1$ along the transport direction to ensure accurate results. We have finally calculated the current flowing at constant bias condition using the post-processing tool TBTrans which is included in the TranSIESTA package [52]. In our transport property simulations, we did not include a buffer layer. However, the setup and parameters were carefully chosen to ensure accurate results. The system was designed to minimize artificial interactions between the transport region and the leads, providing reliable insights into the electronic transport properties.

Results and discussion

Adsorption of NCGs on different heterostructures

Various heterostructures of MX₂ materials have been explored in our previous work [43]. The M elements include Mo, W, Cr, Ir, Ni, Pt, Ru, and Ti, while the X elements are Se, S, Te, and O. We considered twelve heterostructures: MoTe₂/WTe₂, MoS₂/WS₂, MoS₂/NiS₂, MoS₂/RuS₂, MoS₂/PtS₂, WS₂/NiS₂, MoTe₂/WSe₂, WS₂/CrS₂, MoTe₂/WS₂, MoS₂/TiO₂, MoS₂/IrO₂, and MoS₂/WTe₂. To perform an initial selection of the most promising systems as TENG (Triboelectric Nanogenerator) elements, we focused on models exhibiting the largest average charge differences between the two TMD layers. Notably, significant charge differences were observed in the systems MoS₂/WTe₂, MoTe₂/WS₂, MoS₂/IrO₂, and MoS₂/TiO₂. Since a large charge separation enhances triboelectric activity, we prioritized these systems for further analysis. These selected heterostructures were subsequently utilized in gas sensing applications, where their distinct properties were evaluated for potential performance in detecting various gas molecules. In this study, nitrogen-containing gases were optimized on MoS₂/WTe₂, MoTe₂/WS₂, MoS₂/TiO₂ and MoS₂/IrO₂ heterostructures, leveraging the favorable adsorption sites identified in prior studies [56,57]. We have considered the top layer of a bilayer for adsorption of gas molecules. However, we

explored different surface terminations, including sulfur, tellurium, and oxygen, to interact with various gas molecules. These gas molecules adsorbed on all surface terminations, contributing to the gas sensing and adsorption properties. The optimized structures for nitrogen-containing gases are shown in Figs. 1-4, and the adsorption energies and bond distances are detailed in Table 1. For NH_3 , physisorption is observed in both the $\text{MoTe}_2/\text{WS}_2$ and $\text{MoS}_2/\text{WTe}_2$ heterostructures. However, in the $\text{MoS}_2/\text{TiO}_2$ and $\text{MoS}_2/\text{IrO}_2$ heterostructures, NH_3 adsorption energies are -0.68 eV and -0.54 eV, respectively. The adsorption behaviour of gas molecules on the heterostructures varies with the surface terminations. When the surface terminations are sulphur or tellurium, the adsorption energy of gas molecules is lower compared to oxygen-terminated surfaces. This is because oxygen is more electronegative than sulphur and tellurium, leading to stronger interactions with the surface. This strong electron-withdrawing capability enhances the interaction between the gas molecules and the oxygen-terminated surface, leading to higher adsorption energy. On the other hand, sulphur and tellurium, being less electronegative, form weaker interactions with the gas molecules, resulting in lower adsorption energies. These variations in adsorption behaviour are critical for applications like gas sensing, as the strength of the interaction influences the sensitivity and selectivity of the heterostructures for detecting specific gas molecules.

The calculated adsorption distances between NH_3 and the $\text{MoS}_2/\text{WTe}_2$, $\text{MoTe}_2/\text{WS}_2$, $\text{MoS}_2/\text{TiO}_2$ and $\text{MoS}_2/\text{IrO}_2$ heterostructures are 3.04 Å, 2.85 Å, 2.41 Å, and 3.11 Å, respectively. Additionally, the adsorption energy of NO_2 was calculated, showing that NO_2 adsorption on the $\text{MoS}_2/\text{TiO}_2$ heterostructure has the highest adsorption energy of -1.67 eV. The adsorption energies of NO_2 on the $\text{MoS}_2/\text{WTe}_2$, $\text{MoTe}_2/\text{WS}_2$, and $\text{MoS}_2/\text{IrO}_2$ heterostructures are -1.02 eV, -0.78 eV, and -1.13 eV, respectively. The calculated adsorption distances between NO_2 and the heterostructures are 2.80 Å, 2.70 Å, 2.33 Å, and 2.13 Å for $\text{MoS}_2/\text{WTe}_2$, $\text{MoTe}_2/\text{WS}_2$, $\text{MoS}_2/\text{TiO}_2$ and $\text{MoS}_2/\text{IrO}_2$, respectively.

In terms of NO adsorption, the molecule is physisorbed on the $\text{MoTe}_2/\text{WS}_2$ heterostructure but chemisorbed on the $\text{MoS}_2/\text{WTe}_2$, $\text{MoS}_2/\text{TiO}_2$ and $\text{MoS}_2/\text{IrO}_2$ heterostructures. The adsorption energies are -0.34 eV, -2.27 eV, and -1.92 eV for $\text{MoS}_2/\text{WTe}_2$, $\text{MoS}_2/\text{TiO}_2$ and $\text{MoS}_2/\text{IrO}_2$, respectively. The calculated adsorption distances between NO and the $\text{MoS}_2/\text{WTe}_2$, $\text{MoTe}_2/\text{WS}_2$, $\text{MoS}_2/\text{TiO}_2$ and $\text{MoS}_2/\text{IrO}_2$

heterostructures are provided in Table 1. The shorter distances between NO and the $\text{MoS}_2/\text{TiO}_2$ and $\text{MoS}_2/\text{IrO}_2$ heterostructures indicate stronger interactions. In summary, the adsorption energy of nitrogen-containing gases on the $\text{MoS}_2/\text{TiO}_2$ and $\text{MoS}_2/\text{IrO}_2$ heterostructures is higher compared to that on the $\text{MoS}_2/\text{WTe}_2$ and $\text{MoTe}_2/\text{WS}_2$ heterostructures, suggesting stronger interactions with these materials.

Electronic property analysis

To investigate the sensing mechanism of nitrogen-containing gases (NCGs) on $\text{MoS}_2/\text{WTe}_2$, $\text{MoTe}_2/\text{WS}_2$, $\text{MoS}_2/\text{TiO}_2$ and $\text{MoS}_2/\text{IrO}_2$ heterostructures, we analyzed electronic properties, including Bader charge analysis, electron density difference and projected density of states.

Bader charge analysis

The Bader analysis method was employed to obtain the charges of nitrogen containing gases adsorbed on $\text{MoS}_2/\text{WTe}_2$, $\text{MoTe}_2/\text{WS}_2$, $\text{MoS}_2/\text{TiO}_2$ and $\text{MoS}_2/\text{IrO}_2$ heterostructures. The charge of each atom in the heterostructures was determined using the Bader charge analysis method [58], which calculates the charge density within each Bader volume. Each Bader volume represents the charge associated with a specific atom. The total charge was obtained by summing over all atoms in the system, both before and after the adsorption of gas molecules. According to this definition, positive values of indicate a loss of electrons, while negative values imply a gain of electrons. The calculated Bader charge values of NH_3 in $\text{MoS}_2/\text{WTe}_2$, $\text{MoTe}_2/\text{WS}_2$, $\text{MoS}_2/\text{TiO}_2$ and $\text{MoS}_2/\text{IrO}_2$ heterostructures are 0.02 , 0.07 , 0.19 and 0.26 electron, respectively. This confirms that NH_3 acts as an electron donor in all heterostructures, and the charge transfer to the sensing materials is consistent with the adsorption energy.

We observed that NO_2 and NO act as electron acceptors in $\text{MoS}_2/\text{WTe}_2$ and $\text{MoTe}_2/\text{WS}_2$ heterostructures, while they serve as electron donors in $\text{MoS}_2/\text{TiO}_2$ and $\text{MoS}_2/\text{IrO}_2$ heterostructures. Additionally, the results indicate an inconsistency between the adsorption energy of NO_2 and the charge transfer in $\text{MoS}_2/\text{TiO}_2$ and $\text{MoS}_2/\text{IrO}_2$ heterostructures. Specifically, the charge transfer of NO_2 is minimal compared to that of NO in these heterostructures (see Table 1). The lower adsorption energy of NO_2 and the longer bond length between the adsorbate and the

Fig. 1. Optimized adsorption structures of a) NH_3 , b) NO_2 and c) NO on $\text{MoS}_2/\text{WTe}_2$ heterostructure. White (H), Deep blue (N), Red (O), Light blue (W), Orange (Te), Green (Mo) and Yellow (S).

Fig. 2. Optimized adsorption structures of a) NH₃, b) NO₂ and c) NO on MoTe₂/WS₂ heterostructure. White (H), Deep blue (N), Red (O), Light blue (W), Orange (Te), Green (Mo) and Yellow (S).

Fig. 3. Optimized adsorption structures of a) NH₃, b) NO₂ and c) NO on MoS₂/TiO₂ heterostructure. White (H), Deep blue (N), Red (O), Gray (Ti), Green (Mo) and Yellow (S).

surface observed on MoS₂/TiO₂ and MoS₂/IrO₂ heterostructures, compared to NO, indicate weak interactions on these surfaces. Additionally, the oxygen in NO₂ points towards the surface, creating repulsion with the oxygen atoms on the surface, which could inhibit charge transfer of NO₂ on the surface.

Electron density difference and projected density of states analysis

We have further studied electron density difference plots and projected density of states in order to study the orbital interactions of NCGs and the heterostructures. The electron density difference is calculated as follows:

$$\rho_{diff} = \rho_{Total} - \rho_{heterostructure} - \rho_{molecule} \tag{5}$$

where, ρ_{Total} is the electron density distribution of gas molecule

adsorbed on the heterostructure, $\rho_{heterostructure}$ represents the electron density for the heterostructure and $\rho_{molecule}$ is the electron density of gas molecule. We have generated plots using a range of isosurface values to find a balance between clarity and detail. Lower isosurface values are used to highlight subtle density differences and capture delicate re-distributions of electrons. This approach ensures transparency, allowing readers to accurately assess the sensitivity of the analysis and interpret the visualizations effectively. The interaction between the molecule and the MoS₂/IrO₂ surface forms a rectangular configuration. For consistency, all heterostructures were analyzed using the same isosurface value to interpret the electron density associated with different gas molecules. However, when a lower electron density is used for the MoS₂/IrO₂ system, the yellow and cyan curves representing the electron density distributions are far apart, as illustrated in Fig. 5d. Fig. 5 shows

Fig. 4. Optimized adsorption structures of a) NH_3 , b) NO_2 and c) NO on $\text{MoS}_2/\text{IrO}_2$ heterostructure. White (H), Deep blue (N), Red (O), Blue black (Ir), Green (Mo) and Yellow (S).

Table 1

Adsorption energy (E_{ads}) of NCGs, bond distance (d) between gas molecules and heterostructures and bader charge results. After the adsorption of gas molecules on the heterostructure, the distance between the closest atom of the gas molecule and the surface is measured to determine the gas molecule/bilayer distance.

$\text{MoS}_2/\text{WTe}_2$	E_{ads} (eV)	d (Å)	Q (e)
NH_3	0.02	3.04	0.02
NO_2	-1.02	2.80	-0.49
NO	-0.34	2.78	-0.18
$\text{MoTe}_2/\text{WS}_2$	E_{ads} (eV)	d (Å)	Q (e)
NH_3	0.05	2.85	0.07
NO_2	-0.78	2.70	-0.29
NO	0.03	2.60	-0.02
$\text{MoS}_2/\text{TiO}_2$	E_{ads} (eV)	d (Å)	Q (e)
NH_3	-0.68	2.41	0.19
NO_2	-1.67	2.33	0.01
NO	-2.27	2.18	0.23
$\text{MoS}_2/\text{IrO}_2$	E_{ads} (eV)	d (Å)	Q (e)
NH_3	-0.54	3.11	0.26
NO_2	-1.13	2.13	0.02
NO	-1.92	1.87	0.24

the electron density difference plots for nitrogen-containing gases on $\text{MoS}_2/\text{WTe}_2$, $\text{MoTe}_2/\text{WS}_2$, $\text{MoS}_2/\text{TiO}_2$ and $\text{MoS}_2/\text{IrO}_2$ heterostructures. Regions of charge depletion are represented in cyan, while regions of electron accumulation are shown in yellow. Partial electron density depletion and accumulation were observed around NH_3 in each heterostructure. This result aligns with the Bader charge calculations, where NH_3 acts as an electron donor upon adsorption in all heterostructures. Thicker electron density accumulation is observed following NO_2 adsorption on $\text{MoS}_2/\text{WTe}_2$ and $\text{MoTe}_2/\text{WS}_2$ heterostructures, compared to $\text{MoS}_2/\text{TiO}_2$ and $\text{MoS}_2/\text{IrO}_2$ heterostructures. This accumulation indicates that NO_2 accepts electrons from $\text{MoS}_2/\text{WTe}_2$ and $\text{MoTe}_2/\text{WS}_2$, consistent with Bader charge calculations showing NO_2 as an electron acceptor in these heterostructures.

After NO adsorption, thicker electron density accumulation is observed on the $\text{MoS}_2/\text{WTe}_2$ and $\text{MoTe}_2/\text{WS}_2$ heterostructures, while thicker electron density depletion is seen on $\text{MoS}_2/\text{TiO}_2$ and $\text{MoS}_2/\text{IrO}_2$ heterostructures. This finding is consistent with the Bader charge calculations. Figs. 6, 7, 8, and 9 illustrate the projected density of states plots for NH_3 , NO_2 , and NO before and after adsorption on $\text{MoS}_2/\text{WTe}_2$, $\text{MoTe}_2/\text{WS}_2$, $\text{MoS}_2/\text{TiO}_2$ and $\text{MoS}_2/\text{IrO}_2$ heterostructures. These

projected density of states diagrams provide insights into the electronic interactions between the gas molecules and the heterostructures. After adsorption, a notable reduction in the band gap is observed in all heterostructures. This band gap narrowing indicates the formation of new electronic states near the Fermi level, which results from strong interactions between the adsorbed gas molecules and the surface atoms of the heterostructures.

The interaction can involve charge transfer, hybridization of electronic orbitals, or both, depending on the specific gas molecule and surface termination. The PDOS analysis of $\text{MoS}_2/\text{WTe}_2$, $\text{MoTe}_2/\text{WS}_2$, $\text{MoS}_2/\text{TiO}_2$ and $\text{MoS}_2/\text{IrO}_2$ heterostructures shows that Mo, Ti, and W d orbitals and S and Te p-orbitals are the main contributors to the valence band. In the $\text{MoS}_2/\text{WTe}_2$ and $\text{MoTe}_2/\text{WS}_2$ heterostructures, the Te p d-orbitals are the main contributors to the conduction band, with smaller contributions from S p-orbitals. On the other hand, S p-orbitals are the main contributors to the conduction band in both $\text{MoS}_2/\text{TiO}_2$ and $\text{MoS}_2/\text{IrO}_2$ heterostructures with minimal contributions observed from O p-orbitals. The degree of band gap reduction varies across the different heterostructures and gases, reflecting the influence of the structural and electronic properties of each heterostructure on gas adsorption behaviour. A lower band gap after adsorption suggests enhanced conductivity, which is particularly relevant for gas-sensing applications, as it can lead to measurable changes in the material's electrical properties in the presence of specific gas molecules. These findings highlight the strong adsorption capabilities of the heterostructures, further emphasizing their potential for applications such as gas detection and sensing. The choice of heterostructure and gas molecule plays a critical role in determining the extent of interaction and the resulting electronic changes.

Current (I)–Voltage (V) characteristics

To assess the sensing capabilities of the heterostructures for nitrogen-containing gas (NCG) molecules, we investigated their transmission properties. The transport characteristics of $\text{MoS}_2/\text{WTe}_2$, $\text{MoTe}_2/\text{WS}_2$, $\text{MoS}_2/\text{TiO}_2$ and $\text{MoS}_2/\text{IrO}_2$ heterostructures, both with and without adsorbed NCGs, were studied using the TranSIESTA module [52]. The transport setup was modeled with identical electrode materials (left and right), both semi-infinite, while the scattering region, including the NCG molecules, was placed between them. Current was calculated using the Landauer-Büttiker formula [54] across a bias voltage range of 0.0 to 1.0

Fig. 5. Calculated electron density difference on a) MoS₂/WTe₂, b) MoTe₂/WS₂, c) MoS₂/TiO₂, and d) MoS₂/IrO₂ heterostructure. The iso surface level is 0.0005 e/Å³.

Fig. 6. Calculated projected density of states (PDOS) of adsorption of NH₃, NO₂ and NO on MoS₂/WTe₂ heterostructure. The Fermi level has been set to 0 eV.

Fig. 7. Calculated projected density of states (PDOS) of adsorption of NH₃, NO₂ and NO on MoTe₂/WS₂ heterostructure. The Fermi level has been set to 0 eV.

Fig. 8. Calculated projected density of states (PDOS) of adsorption of NH₃, NO₂ and NO on MoS₂/TiO₂ heterostructure. The Fermi level has been set to 0 eV.

Fig. 9. Calculated projected density of states (PDOS) of adsorption of NH₃, NO₂ and NO on MoS₂/IrO₂ heterostructure. The Fermi level has been set to 0 eV.

V.

Fig. 10 shows the current–voltage (I-V) characteristics of NCGs before and after adsorption on the MoS₂/WTe₂ heterostructure. Overall, the current responses remain small before and after NCG adsorption on all heterostructures and are generally within the same order of magnitude, except for NH₃ and NO adsorbed on the MoS₂/IrO₂ heterostructure at a bias voltage of 1.0 V. After NH₃, NO₂, and NO adsorption on MoS₂/WTe₂, the current response rises with increasing voltage. However, for NO₂ adsorption on MoS₂/WTe₂, the current response stabilizes beyond 0.8 V and decreases for NO adsorption at 1.0 V. This confirms that sensitivity begins at a low bias voltage of 0.1 V, indicating low power consumption.

The I-V curves for MoTe₂/WS₂, MoS₂/TiO₂ and MoS₂/IrO₂ heterostructures, with and without adsorbed gases, are presented in Fig. 10. Changes in current are minimal after NH₃ and NO adsorption on MoTe₂/WS₂ but increase significantly with NO₂. Additionally, current response rises with bias voltage, both with and without NCG adsorption on MoS₂/TiO₂, with a slight increase after 1.0 V for NH₃ and NO adsorption. Fig. 10 shows that NO₂ adsorption on MoS₂/IrO₂ leads to minor current increases compared to NH₃ and NO adsorption. Calculated sensitivity for NH₃ is generally lower than for NO and NO₂ in MoS₂/WTe₂, MoTe₂/WS₂ and MoS₂/TiO₂ but is higher than for NO₂ in MoS₂/IrO₂. Consequently, our results indicate that MoS₂/WTe₂, MoTe₂/WS₂ and MoS₂/TiO₂

Fig. 10. Current-Voltage curves for the adsorption of NCGs on bilayers (MoS₂/WTe₂, MoTe₂/WS₂, MoS₂/TiO₂ and MoS₂/IrO₂).

heterostructures are more sensitive to NO_x gases. These calculations reveal that MoS₂/WTe₂ shows greater sensitivity to NO than to NH₃ and NO₂, indicating a high selectivity for NO under the given conditions. Similarly, NO₂ demonstrates significant sensitivity in MoS₂/TiO₂ and MoS₂/IrO₂ heterostructures, while NO shows higher sensitivity in MoS₂/IrO₂ structure. Overall, the findings indicate that NO_x molecules have greater sensitivity in MoS₂/WTe₂, MoTe₂/WS₂, MoS₂/TiO₂ and MoS₂/IrO₂ at lower applied bias voltages, contributing to improved selectivity for NO and NO₂ in these heterostructures. Variations in the I-V curves are observed in the MoS₂/WTe₂, MoTe₂/WS₂, MoS₂/TiO₂ and MoS₂/IrO₂ bilayers, which are perturbed by the presence of different gas molecules. Specifically, the presence of NH₃ decreases the current flow in all four bilayer systems. This reduction is attributed to the NH₃ molecule transferring a significant number of electrons to the MoS₂/WTe₂, MoTe₂/WS₂, MoS₂/TiO₂ and MoS₂/IrO₂ bilayers surfaces, which inhibits free electron mobility by creating scattering centers, thereby decreasing the overall current flow in the device. In contrast, the presence of NO₂ and NO increases the current flow on the MoS₂/WTe₂ and MoTe₂/WS₂ surfaces, which promotes free electron mobility through the scattering centers, thereby enhancing the overall current flow in the device. These insights are valuable for developing gas sensors with enhanced selectivity and practical applications.

Band gap and recovery time

The relationship between band gap and electrical conductivity is an important factor in understanding the gas sensing properties of heterostructures. In our study, we investigated how the band gap influences the gas sensing properties of MoS₂/WTe₂, MoTe₂/WS₂, MoS₂/TiO₂ and MoS₂/IrO₂ heterostructures for detecting nitrogen-containing gases (NCGs). The relationship between band gap and electrical conductivity is described as follows [59,60]:

$$\sigma \propto \exp\left(\frac{-E_g}{2kT}\right) \quad (6)$$

where σ , k , E_g and T represents the electrical conductivity, the Boltzmann constant, the band gap, and temperature, respectively. The

calculated bandgap values for the pristine heterostructures MoS₂/WTe₂, MoTe₂/WS₂, MoS₂/TiO₂, and MoS₂/IrO₂ are 1.81 eV, 1.93 eV, 2.62 eV, and 2.83 eV, respectively. Upon adsorption of gas molecules, the band gap decreases across all heterostructures, indicating a change in electrical conductivity due to the alteration of their electronic properties. Additionally, we calculated the recovery times of these heterostructures (MoS₂/WTe₂, MoTe₂/WS₂, MoS₂/TiO₂, and MoS₂/IrO₂) at various temperatures. The results show that NH₃ exhibits the shortest recovery times for all heterostructures. Furthermore, NO₂ and NO molecules have shorter recovery times on MoS₂/WTe₂, MoTe₂/WS₂ compared to their recovery times on MoS₂/IrO₂, and MoS₂/TiO₂. This trend highlights a relationship between adsorption energy and recovery time: lower adsorption energy corresponds to shorter recovery times, while higher adsorption energy leads to longer recovery times. Moreover, the recovery time increases with rising temperature, reflecting the thermally activated nature of the desorption process.

The observed changes in band gap before and after the adsorption of nitrogen-containing gases (NCGs) on the various heterostructures (MoS₂/WTe₂ and MoTe₂/WS₂) are crucial indicators of their sensitivity as gas sensors (Fig. S1 and S2). As shown in Figs. S1 and S2, the band gap decreases after the adsorption of gas molecules on the heterostructures. However, the changes in the band gap between different gas molecules are relatively small, and their respective band gap curves appear to overlap. Despite this apparent overlap, there are still subtle differences between the band gaps corresponding to each gas molecule. These differences, although small, indicate variations in the interaction strength and the extent of charge transfer or orbital hybridization between the gas molecules and the heterostructure surfaces. The overlapping trends suggest that the electronic structures of the heterostructures are modified in a similar manner upon gas adsorption, but the specific electronic states introduced or shifted depend on the type of gas molecule. Such distinctions, even if minor, can play a critical role in applications like gas sensing, where sensitivity relies on detecting these subtle changes.

A significant change in band gap implies a corresponding alteration in the conductivity of the material. In this context, the observed band gap variations suggest that the conductivity of the heterostructures can be enhanced upon exposure to NCGs. This is a critical factor in determining the suitability of these materials for gas sensing applications. Evaluating the recovery time is a crucial aspect of assessing the performance of gas sensors. It provides valuable information about the sensor's ability to return to its initial state after being exposed to a specific gas. A shorter recovery time indicates a faster response and regeneration of the sensor, which is desirable for practical applications. The recovery time (τ) can be calculated as follows:

$$\tau = \nu^{-1} \exp\left(\frac{-E_{\text{ads}}}{kT}\right) \quad (7)$$

where k , T and ν^{-1} , E_{ads} is Boltzmann constant, temperature, the attempted frequency of the molecules and adsorption energy, respectively. It's valuable to know that the recovery times are shorter at room temperature in MoS₂/WTe₂ and MoTe₂/WS₂ heterostructures. Additionally, the observation of shorter recovery times for NH₃ in MoS₂/IrO₂ and MoS₂/TiO₂ heterostructures further highlights their potential for efficient desorption and sensor reusability. This means that NH₃ molecules have a tendency to desorb or detach from the surface of the heterostructures more quickly than NO₂ and NO molecules, indicating faster recovery times. It suggests that the gas sensors utilizing MoS₂/WTe₂ and MoTe₂/WS₂ bilayers have the potential to be efficiently recycled. As shown in Table 2, as the temperature increases the recovery times increases. This information is significant for practical applications, especially in gas sensing or catalytic processes. It's worth noting that these findings highlight the potential for these heterostructures in environmental and industrial applications where the detection and removal of NH₃, NO₂, and NO gases are important.

Table 2

Recovery time (τ in second) of NCGs in MoS₂/WTe₂, MoTe₂/WS₂, MoS₂/TiO₂ and MoS₂/IrO₂ heterostructures at 300 K, 400 K and 500 K.

MoS ₂ /WTe ₂	τ (300)	τ (400)	τ (500)	band gap
NH ₃	1.06×10^{-12}	1.05×10^{-12}	1.04×10^{-12}	0.76
NO ₂	1.47×10^5	7.53	2.00×10^{-2}	0.82
NO	7.14×10^{-7}	2.45×10^{-8}	3.26×10^{-9}	0.71
MoTe ₂ /WS ₂	τ (300)	τ (400)	τ (500)	band gap
NH ₃	2.34×10^{-12}	1.89×10^{-12}	1.66×10^{-12}	1.53
NO ₂	13.4	7.00×10^{-3}	7.50×10^{-5}	1.40
NO	1.06×10^{-12}	1.04×10^{-12}	1.03×10^{-12}	1.47
MoS ₂ /TiO ₂	τ (300)	τ (400)	τ (500)	band gap
NH ₃	0.27	3.81×10^{-4}	7.34×10^{-6}	1.51
NO ₂	1.28×10^{16}	1.20×10^9	7.30×10^4	1.43
NO	1.61×10^{26}	4.51×10^{16}	8.44×10^{12}	1.31
MoS ₂ /IrO ₂	τ (300)	τ (400)	τ (500)	band gap
NH ₃	1.23×10^{-3}	6.51×10^{-6}	2.84×10^{-7}	1.82
NO ₂	1.05×10^7	182	0.256	2.11
NO	2.06×10^{20}	1.73×10^{12}	2.46×10^7	1.91

Conclusions

We conducted first-principles calculations to investigate the sensing properties of toxic gases, namely NH₃, NO₂, and NO, on MoS₂/WTe₂, MoTe₂/WS₂, MoS₂/TiO₂ and MoS₂/IrO₂ heterostructures. Our findings indicate that NH₃ physisorbs onto MoS₂/WTe₂ and MoTe₂/WS₂ heterostructures, with adsorption energies of -0.68 eV and -0.54 eV for MoS₂/TiO₂ and MoS₂/IrO₂ heterostructures, respectively. The adsorption energies of NO₂ and NO are higher in MoS₂/TiO₂ and MoS₂/IrO₂ heterostructures. Bader charge analysis reveals that the charge transfer between nitrogen-containing gases (NCGs) and the heterostructures is less than 0.5 electrons. Specifically, NO₂ and NO act as electron acceptors in MoS₂/WTe₂ and MoTe₂/WS₂ heterostructures, while they act as electron donors in MoS₂/TiO₂ and MoS₂/IrO₂ heterostructures. Further electronic interactions were explored using electron density difference and projected density of states calculations, which showed substantial electron donation from MoS₂/WTe₂ and MoTe₂/WS₂ heterostructures to NO and NO₂. Additionally, electron transport calculations demonstrated minimal changes in current response before and after NCG adsorption on the heterostructures. The simulated current-voltage (I-V) curves of the NO_x molecules on MoS₂/WTe₂, MoTe₂/WS₂, MoS₂/TiO₂ and MoS₂/IrO₂ heterostructures revealed that NH₃ induced only small changes in current response, while NO and NO₂ led to significant current response changes within a specific bias range. This suggests that the heterostructures exhibit varying sensitivities to different gases, which is valuable for potential gas sensing applications. Our study identifies specific heterostructures (MoS₂/WTe₂, MoTe₂/WS₂, MoS₂/TiO₂ and MoS₂/IrO₂) with excellent potential for NH₃ detection, considering factors like adsorption energy, electronic property changes, and recovery times. Moreover, MoS₂/WTe₂ and MoTe₂/WS₂ heterostructures are also promising candidates for NO₂ and NO detection.

Generally, all results demonstrate that the recovery time for NO_x sensing in MoS₂/WTe₂ and MoTe₂/WS₂ heterostructures is sufficient for recycling gas sensors at room temperature. However, we observed that the recovery time for NO_x molecules in MoS₂/TiO₂ and MoS₂/IrO₂ is longer compared to MoS₂/WTe₂ and MoTe₂/WS₂. Our results show that MoS₂/WTe₂ and MoTe₂/WS₂ exhibit lower recovery times for NO_x molecules. Furthermore, the calculation of the I/V characteristics reveals that MoS₂/TiO₂ and MoS₂/IrO₂ have higher current flow with increasing voltage, making them unsuitable for achieving stable charge separation. These findings indicate that the most promising heterostructures for building sensor devices are MoS₂/WTe₂ and MoTe₂/WS₂. The insights gained from this study offer valuable information for the development of sensitive and reliable gas sensors. The specificity and sensitivity of these heterostructures to different toxic gases could have significant implications for real-world applications.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jemal Yimer Damte: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Hasan Ataalite:** Writing – review & editing, Validation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rinp.2025.108183>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Tang X, Du A, Kou L. Gas sensing and capturing based on two-dimensional layered materials: Overview from theoretical perspective. *Wiley Interdiscip Rev Comput Mol Sci* 2018;8:1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcms.1361>.
- Yeh CH, Hsieh DW. Combined density functional theory calculation and non-equilibrium Green's function approach to predict the sensitivity of nitrogen-containing gases over Pt/TenS₂-n monolayers (n = 0–2). *FlatChem* 2022;35:100418. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.flatc.2022.100418>.
- Flanagan E, Malmqvist E, Gustafsson S, Oudin A. Estimated public health benefits of a low-emission zone in Malmö. *Sweden Environ Res* 2022;214:114124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2022.114124>.
- World Health Organization. *World Health Statistics - Monitoring Health for the SDGs*. World Heal Organ 2016:1.121.
- Ghebreyesus TA, Fore H, Birtanov Y, Jakab Z. Primary health care for the 21st century, universal health coverage, and the Sustainable Development Goals. *Lancet* 2018;392:1371–2. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(18\)32556-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(18)32556-X).
- Kumar S, Pavelyev V, Mishra P, Tripathi N, Sharma P, Calle F. A review on 2D transition metal di-chalcogenides and metal oxide nanostructures based NO₂ gas sensors. *Mater Sci Semicond Process* 2020;107:104865. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mssp.2019.104865>.
- Bernard SM, Samet JM, Grambsch A, Ebl KL, Romieu I. The potential impacts of climate variability and change on air pollution-related health effects in the United States. *Environ Health Perspect* 2001;109:199–209. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3435010>.
- Chen Y, Zhang L, Zhao Y, Zhang L, Zhang J, Liu M, et al. High-Resolution Ammonia Emissions from Nitrogen Fertilizer Application in China during 2005–2020. *Atmosphere (base)* 2022;13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos13081297>.
- Dindorkar SS, Yadav A. Monolayered Silicon Carbide for Sensing Toxic Gases: a Comprehensive Study Based on the First-principle Density Functional Theory. *SILICON* 2022;14:11771–9. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12633-022-01899-x>.
- Hesterberg TW, Bunn WB, McClellan RO, Hamade AK, Long CM, Valberg PA. Critical review of the human data on short-term nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) exposures: Evidence for NO₂ no-effect levels. *Crit Rev Toxicol* 2009;39:743–81. <https://doi.org/10.3109/10408440903294945>.
- Salih E, Ayesb AI. First principle study of transition metals codoped MoS₂ as a gas sensor for the detection of NO and NO₂ gases. *Phys E Low-Dimensional Syst Nanostructures* 2021;131:114736. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physe.2021.114736>.
- Warner JX, Dickerson RR, Wei Z, Strow LL, Wang Y, Liang Q. Increased atmospheric ammonia over the world's major agricultural areas detected from space. *Geophys Res Lett* 2017;44:2875–84. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016GL072305>.
- Zhou J, Wang C, Zhang X, Jiang L, Wu R. Advances in two-dimensional layered materials for gas sensing. *Mater Sci Eng R Reports* 2024;161:100872. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mser.2024.100872>.
- Broza YY, Vishinkin R, Barash O, Nakhleh MK, Haick H. Synergy between Nanomaterials and Volatile Organic Compounds for Non-Invasive Medical Evaluation 2018;vol. 47. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c8cs00317c>.
- Galstyan V, Bhandari MP, Sberveglieri V, Sberveglieri G, Comini E. Metal oxide nanostructures in food applications: Quality control and packaging. *Chemosensors* 2018;6:1–21. <https://doi.org/10.3390/chemosensors6020016>.
- Jalal AH, Alam F, Roychoudhury S, Umasankar Y, Pala N, Bhansali S. Prospects and Challenges of Volatile Organic Compound Sensors in Human Healthcare. *ACS Sensors* 2018;3:1246–63. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssensors.8b00400>.
- Mercante LA, Andre RS, Mattoso LHC, Correa DS. Electrospun Ceramic Nanofibers and Hybrid-Nanofiber Composites for Gas Sensing. *ACS Appl Nano Mater* 2019;2:4026–42. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnm.9b01176>.
- Pavase TR, Lin H, Shaikh Q ul ain, Hussain S, Li Z, Ahmed I, et al. Recent advances of conjugated polymer (CP) nanocomposite-based chemical sensors and their applications in food spoilage detection: a comprehensive review 2018;vol. 273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2018.06.118>.
- Pawar KK, Kumar A, Mirzaei A, Kumar M, Kim HW, Kim SS. 2D nanomaterials for realization of flexible and wearable gas sensors: A review. *Chemosphere* 2024;352:141234. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2024.141234>.
- Babar V, Vovusha H, Schwingschlögl U. Density functional theory analysis of gas adsorption on monolayer and few layer transition metal dichalcogenides: implications for sensing. *ACS Appl Nano Mater* 2019;2:6076–80. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnm.9b01642>.
- Cui H, Zhang G, Zhang X, Tang J. Rh-doped MoSe₂ as a toxic gas scavenger: A first-principles study. *Nanoscale Adv* 2019;1:772–80. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c8na00233a>.
- Goel N, Kunal K, Kushwaha A, Kumar M. Metal oxide semiconductors for gas sensing. *Eng Reports* 2023;5:1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eng.212604>.
- Ji H, Zeng W, Li Y. Gas sensing mechanisms of metal oxide semiconductors: A focus review. *Nanoscale* 2019;11:22664–84. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9nr07699a>.
- Shim YS, Kwon KC, Suh JM, Choi KS, Song YG, Sohn W, et al. Synthesis of Numerous Edge Sites in MoS₂ via SiO₂ Nanorods Platform for Highly Sensitive Gas Sensor. *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces* 2018;10:31594–602. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaami.8b08114>.
- Szary MJ, Florjan DM, Bąbalek JA. Selective Detection of Carbon Monoxide on P-Block Doped Monolayers of MoTe₂. *ACS Sensors* 2022;7:272–85. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssensors.1c02246>.
- Xu Z. Adsorption and sensing mechanisms of Ni-doped PtTe₂ monolayer upon NO₂ and O₃ in air-insulated switchgears. *RSC Adv* 2023;13:18129–37. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d3ra03030j>.
- Cho SY, Kim SJ, Lee Y, Kim JS, Bin JW, Yoo HW, et al. Highly enhanced gas adsorption properties in vertically aligned MoS₂ layers. *ACS Nano* 2015;9:9314–21. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.5b04504>.
- Kim Y, Kang SK, Oh NC, Lee HD, Lee SM, Park J, et al. Improved sensitivity in Schottky contacted two-dimensional MoS₂ gas sensor. *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces* 2019;11:38902–9. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaami.9b10861>.
- Meng Z, Stolz RM, Mendecki L, Mirica KA. Electrically-transduced chemical sensors based on two-dimensional nanomaterials. *Chem Rev* 2019;119:478–598. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.8b00311>.
- Ko JK, Park IH, Hong K, Kwon KC. Recent advances in chemoresistive gas sensors using two-dimensional materials. *Nanomaterials* 2024;14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano14171397>.
- Joshi N, Braunger ML, Shimizu FM, Riul A, Oliveira ON. Two-Dimensional transition metal dichalcogenides for gas sensing applications 2020:131–55. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-38101-1_4.
- Kim Y, Lee S, Song JG, Ko KY, Woo WJ, Lee SW, et al. 2D transition metal dichalcogenide heterostructures for p- and n-type photovoltaic self-powered gas sensor. *Adv Funct Mater* 2020;30:1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202003360>.
- Lee E, Yoon YS, Kim DJ. Two-dimensional transition metal dichalcogenides and metal oxide hybrids for gas sensing. *ACS Sensors* 2018;3:2045–60. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssensors.8b01077>.
- Li BL, Wang J, Zou HL, Garaj S, Lim CT, Xie J, et al. Low-dimensional transition metal dichalcogenide nanostructures based sensors. *Adv Funct Mater* 2016;26:7034–56. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.201602136>.
- Ping J, Fan Z, Sindoro M, Ying Y, Zhang H. Recent advances in sensing applications of two-dimensional transition metal dichalcogenide nanosheets and their composites. *Adv Funct Mater* 2017;27:1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.201605817>.
- Late DJ, Doneux T, Bougouma M. Single-layer MoSe₂ based NH₃ gas sensor. *Appl Phys Lett* 2014;105. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4903358>.
- Panigrahi P, Hussain T, Kartan A, Ahuja R. Elemental substitution of two-dimensional transition metal dichalcogenides (MoSe₂ and MoTe₂): implications for enhanced gas sensing. *ACS Sensors* 2019;4:2646–53. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssensors.9b01044>.
- Yuan W, Liu A, Huang L, Li C, Shi G. High-performance NO₂ sensors based on chemically modified graphene. *Adv Mater* 2013;25:766–71. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201203172>.
- Baek J, Yin D, Liu N, Omkaram I, Jung C, Im H, et al. A highly sensitive chemical gas detecting transistor based on highly crystalline CVD-grown MoSe₂ films. *Nano Res* 2017;10:1861–71. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12274-016-1291-7>.
- Cho B, Hahm MG, Choi M, Yoon J, Kim AR, Lee YJ, et al. Charge-transfer-based gas sensing using atomic-layer MoS₂. *Sci Rep* 2015;5:8052. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep08052>.

- [41] Perkins FK, Friedman AL, Cobas E, Campbell PM, Jernigan GG, Jonker BT. Chemical vapor sensing with monolayer MoS₂. *Nano Lett* 2013;13:668–73. <https://doi.org/10.1021/nl3043079>.
- [42] Schedin F, Geim AK, Morozov SV, Hill EW, Blake P, Katsnelson MI, et al. Detection of individual gas molecules adsorbed on graphene. *Nat Mater* 2007;6:652–5. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmat1967>.
- [43] Damte JY, Houska J. Tribo-piezoelectric nanogenerators for energy harvesting: a first-principles study. *Sustain Energy Fuels* 2024;8:4213–20. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d4se00498a>.
- [44] Soler JM, Artacho E, Gale JD, García A, Junquera J, Ordejón P, et al. The SIESTA method for ab initio order-N materials simulation. *J Phys Condens Matter* 2002;14:2745–79. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0953-8984/14/11/302>.
- [45] Artacho E, Sánchez-Portal D, Ordejón P, García A, Soler JM. Linear-scaling ab-initio calculations for large and complex systems. *Phys Status Solidi Basic Res* 1999;215:809–17. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1521-3951\(199909\)215:1<809::AID-PSSB809>3.0.CO;2-0](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1521-3951(199909)215:1<809::AID-PSSB809>3.0.CO;2-0).
- [46] Troullier N, Martins JL. Efficient pseudopotentials for plane-wave calculations. *PhysRevB* 1991;43:1993–2006. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.43.1993>.
- [47] Cammarata A, Polcar T. Tailoring nanoscale friction in MX₂ transition metal dichalcogenides. *Inorg Chem* 2015;54:5739–44. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.inorgchem.5b00431>.
- [48] Belviso F, Cammarata A, Missaoui J, Polcar T. Effect of electric fields in low-dimensional materials: Nanofrictional response as a case study. *PhysRevB* 2020;102:1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.102.155433>.
- [49] Lee K, Murray ED, Kong L, Lundqvist BI, Langreth DC. Higher-accuracy van der Waals density functional. *Phys Rev B - Condens Matter Mater Phys* 2010;82:3–6. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.82.081101>.
- [50] Klime J, Bowler DR, Michaelides A. Van der Waals density functionals applied to solids. *Phys Rev B - Condens Matter Mater Phys* 2011;83:1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.83.195131>.
- [51] Obligacion JKA, Putungan DB. 2D 1T'-MoS₂-WS₂ van der Waals heterostructure for hydrogen evolution reaction: Dispersion-corrected density functional theory calculations. *Mater Res Express* 2020;7:75506. <https://doi.org/10.1088/2053-1591/aba70a>.
- [52] Papior N, Lorente N, Frederiksen T, García A, Brandbyge M. Improvements on non-equilibrium and transport Green function techniques: The next-generation TRANSIESTA. *Comput Phys Commun* 2017;212:8–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpc.2016.09.022>.
- [53] Malcioğlu OB, Erkoç Ş. Functionality of C(4,4) carbon nanotube as molecular detector. *J Nanosci Nanotechnol* 2008;8:469–78. <https://doi.org/10.1166/jnn.2008.D020>.
- [54] Bttiker M, Imry Y, Landauer R, Pinhas S. Generalized many-channel conductance formula with application to small rings. *PhysRevB* 1985;31:6207–15. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.31.6207>.
- [55] Shin S, Kaviany M. Interflake thermal conductance of edge-passivated graphene. *Phys Rev B - Condens Matter Mater Phys* 2011;84:1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.84.235433>.
- [56] Chakraborty D, Johari P. First-Principles Investigation of the 1T-HfTe₂ Nanosheet for Selective Gas Sensing. *ACS Appl Nano Mater* 2020;3:5160–71. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsanm.0c00500>.
- [57] Yue Qu, Zhengzheng SC, Shao JL. Adsorption of gas molecules on monolayer MoS₂ and effect of applied electric field. *Nanoscale Res Lett* 2013;2(8):425. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1556-276X-8-425>.
- [58] Henkelman G, Arnaldsson A, Jónsson H. A fast and robust algorithm for Bader decomposition of charge density. *Comput Mater Sci* 2006;36:354–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.commatsci.2005.04.010>.
- [59] Ahmadi A, Hadipour NL, Kamfirooz M, Bagheri Z. Theoretical study of aluminum nitride nanotubes for chemical sensing of formaldehyde. *Sensors Actuators, B Chem* 2012;161:1025–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2011.12.001>.
- [60] Yeh CH, Lin WY, Jiang JC. Enhancement of chlorobenzene sensing by doping aluminum on nanotubes: A DFT study. *Appl Surf Sci* 2020;514:145897. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2020.145897>.